

STUDENTS' PERCEPTION TOWARD VIDEO MAKING TASK IN ENGLISH TO IMPROVING STUDENTS' SPEAKING SKILLS A STUDY AT DIPA MAKASSAR UNIVERSITY

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Abstract

Techniques that teachers can use to improve students' speaking skills and minimize student errors are now becoming prevalent. In a modern era, teachers usually combine their lessons with technological tools to improve students' language skills. This study discusses students' perception about video making task in improving students speaking skills. The type of research design is mixed method. The population of this research were 219 from Systems Information Department students, Dipa Makassar University and 89 students were selected as the sample. The data collection used questionnaire distribution by Google Form and interview. The purpose of this research was to explore the implementation and the effect of video making task also to determine students' perception of the learning process in their courses by using video making task in improving their speaking skills. The result of this research indicated that the implementation of video making task in improving students speaking skills encountered several difficulties such as the aspects of students' motivation in video making task, students' experienced differences from preparing courses, students' difficulties in pronunciation and the difficulties that influential to students' self-study and self-correction and students have positive perceptions toward video making task in improving their speaking skills.

Keywords: Perception, Speaking Skills, Video, Effect, Improve

1. INTRODUCTION

There are many techniques that teachers and students can use to improve students' speaking skills and reduce student errors are now becoming prevalent (Lazaraton 2001, Harmer 2007). Methods and techniques have revolved around second language teaching which have gained both supports and criticism from educational practices and curriculum developers. They mention the second exercise to a lower level, such as describing pictures in pairs or making up stories from a series of pictures, and exercises at a higher level, such as describing diagrams or discuss current issues. Teachers from different areas often ask students to become actively involved in simulations and role-playing games. In the simulation, students act as if they are inside real life situation. Role playing games simulate their real world in the same way, but

students are assigned specific roles – they are told who they are and often what they think about a certain subject. They have to speak and act from their new character point of view.

In a modern era, teachers usually combine their lessons with technological tools to improve students' language skills. When someone mentions technology in language classes the first impetus is to think about computer technology, especially since computers have penetrated the everyday human home and workplace context. Technology includes everything from audio cassettes, to videos to such as cameras, LCD projectors, smartphones, etc. (Brown, 2007). One of the current trend of EFL teaching instrument is about video making task. This task is reported to play roles in dealing with anxiety. It is believed that Anxiety is one of the factors influencing students' speaking performance in the classroom. A video making task is an alternative strategy that can decrease anxiety besides it provides a positive influence on students' self-assessment of speaking task.

Nowadays, the lecturer in English subject at the Information Systems Department, Dipa Makassar University has a new technique to improve students' speaking skills, especially during a pandemic and the lecture process is carried out online. The technique is called video making task. A new modern technique learning that asks students to record their activity or conversations using camera to improve their speaking skills. With this technique, students will be able to use a technology such as camera and smartphone, and they record themselves to evaluate how good their speaking is (Kirkgoz, 2011). After the video is collected, the lecturer checked student videos and give score. There are five aspects used in assessing speaking skills, namely grammar language/structure (grammar), vocabulary, fluency, pronunciation, and comprehension. Moreover, the video making task is not only given by English courses, but also other courses as well.

In video making process, students usually make it not just once, but many times until their pronunciations as good as possible they can, this process called repetition and correction. Students will improve their speaking skill with this process of video making (Savas, 2012,). In video making task technique, lecturers may face unresponsive or uncooperative students without knowing the reasons, whether the lecturers and their students have opposing views about what should occur in giving video making task to students and whether or not the students achieve the video making task aims.

In this era, teaching and learning with the help of digital videos have been very common in education for the last couple of decades. Even though the use of video has always been present in education, the introduction of digital video parallel to video capturing and editing software in personal computer has led to an increase in individual use on self-recorded by both teachers and learners. (Savas, 2012).

In addition, the learners who are studying English in a non-English speaking setting, need to experience real communicative situations so that they will learn how to express their own views and opinions freely and to develop their own fluency and accuracy which are very essential for the success of FL communication.

Therefore, the investigation in providing the data about students' perceptions on video making task in improving students' speaking skills are needed to know whether the aim of video making task in English that given by lecturers was reached or not and to know the level of students' perceptions related to the effectiveness of video making task to improve their speaking skills.

Based upon the description above, the students' perceptions on video making task in English is needed to know whether it improves their speaking skills or not and whether students can achieve the lecturers' aim in video making task. Therefore, the researcher is really interested in finding more about the students' perception on video making task in English in improving students' speaking ability. Based on this fact, the researcher is interested in conducting the research about "Students' Perception toward Video Making Task in English to Improving Students Speaking Skills at Dipa Makassar University"

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

There has been an overwhelming of studies that venture into the effect of video in language teaching both in ESL and EFL context. Most of the investigation revolve around the positive effect of making video as productive teaching instrument especially in EFL classroom contexts. A study conducted by Agus Darmuki (2020) entitled "Efforts to Improve Student Speaking Ability Using Google Meet Application Media Based Uploading Video Assignments on YouTube during the Covid-19 Pandemic" found that video exercises enabled the learners figure out their own weaknesses and strengths in language learning. In other words, the utilization of support media in a classroom was very useful for the students. It creates a self-learning and can make them have good confidence in English communication.

Another important documentation about video was ventured into by Theresia Katiandagho et al. (2022) entitled, Students' Perception on the use of YouTube to develop their vocabulary. Most of the respondents had positive responses about the use of YouTube to develop their vocabulary. Since then YouTube has been marked as a tool to provide teaching resource and enhanced learning experience. The findings confirm that university students have positive perceptions on the use of YouTube especially at Faculty of Humanities, English Department Sam Ratulangi University.

Another important documentation was performed by Dewi Khawa (2020) who investigated the effectiveness of video-making task in students speaking skill. The study was undertaken by applying control and experimental class and by means of random sampling techniques. The study comes up with the finding that confirmed that Video-making task is a good alternative in teaching English because it opens students' creatively and their and their self-correction in speaking.

The last important documentation was performed by Zainuddin (2016) who investigated students' perceptions on video making task to improve students' speaking skills. Using a qualitative method, the researcher employed field observations and questionnaires to answer the research objectives. He found that most of students like the video making task and they

think that the task is interesting and useful for them to improve their speaking skills. Video making task enable the students to improve some speaking components such as vocabulary, pronunciation, comprehension, and fluency except grammar.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objectives of the present study is to explore the impact of implemented video making task and explain the effect of video making task in improving students' speaking skills. In addition, the study also seeks to elucidate what perception these EFL learners have as a result of Video Making Task in EFL

4. METHOD

To enable the researcher to come up with valid and reliable findings regarding students' perceptions mixed method was applied. Data collection was performed in July 2023 by distributing perception questionnaires to 219 EFL learners at Department of Information System Universitas DIPA Makassar. The samples were purposively chosen by involving only those students who have performed oral presentation in English for Academic Purpose. As many as eighty nine (89) best completed questionnaire were selected to account for as refined data for analysis. Interview was also conducted to comply with qualitative parameter for the study. Data were then analyzed by means of both quantitative and qualitative paradigm.

5. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

5.1. a. Findings (questionnaire)

Table 1: Motivation and Confidence

Questions	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
I am motivated to participate in video making task in English	3	12	64	10
I have no problem with learning using video	1	39	42	7
I can enjoy the course with video making task	2	19	61	7
I am confident to initiate communication with people in English after video making task	4	29	47	9
I am comfortable to communicate using English after implemented video making task	3	22	59	5
I can properly follow the course of English for presentation and communication and English for academic purpose courses	1	6	73	9

As shown in table there is a prevalence of perceptions among the students under investigation. The responses regarding their preference about video making task vary most probably due to several factors such as personality, learning styles and learning preferences. Overall, the perception indicate a very strong preferences in the area of video making task.

Table 2: Learning Autonomy

Questions	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
I can properly correct my mistakes when doing video making task	1	6	66	16
I can properly understand the assignments and complete them	1	6	66	16
I can properly share my ideas during video making process	2	6	70	11
I can Easily get the learning materials		4	72	13

As shown in the table learning autonomy appears to be the most favorable among the learners. Only a small proportion of those are not in agreements with the idea of learning autonomy. This data confirm a necessary consideration for teachers to provide independent learning for EFL context in Indonesia especially in that institution of DIPA Makassar.

Table 3: Learning Focus

Questions	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
I can focus to the courses easily	1	7	67	14
Video making task didn't distracted other courses assignment	3	11	66	9
I am not distracted by other activities during video making task process	2	49	30	8

As shown in the table disparity regarding the learning focus is prevalent among these learners. It appears that video making task generates the learners' attention that may lead to productive learning outcomes.

Table 4: Learning Expectation

Questions	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
I set my personal expectation for my video task	1	6	71	11
The video task is aligned with my expectations	1	23	56	9
The materials for the video task are equal in quality to conventional of the courses	1	5	68	15
I am satisfied with how the learning materials were delivered	2	7	66	14
I am satisfied with how the English for presentation and communication and English for academic purpose courses was managed	1	7	67	14

As shown in the table learning expectation presents disparities among the learners. Learners have the strong tendency to be in favor of video making task. Only relatively very small number of samples who are not in favor of this learning domains.

Table 5: Learning Experiences

Questions	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
I can understand the topic of the English for presentation and communication course without difficulties	1	4	72	12
I can understand the topic of English for academic purpose course	1	4	76	9
I can understand aspects of speaking		6	59	24
I can properly practice speaking in English		5	46	38
I can understand how to do video making		5	68	16
I can properly practice presentation in English		4	64	21
I can understand how to pronounce unfamiliar vocabulary		4	56	29
I can practice my speaking skill fluency		4	55	30
I can understand how to determine the topic on my video task	1	3	68	17
I can practice determining my ideas on my video task	1	4	72	12
I understand the aims of my video making task	1	1	69	18
I can practice my editing skill	1	2	69	17

As shown in the table there is a prevalence of agreement and disagreement regarding learning expectations. Only a very small proportions of the students were in disagreement about this domain. The data confirm that the video making task has very strong and positive effect to the EFL learners.

5.1. b. Findings (Interview)

The interview questions were set up in such a way that could elicit realistic responses, “What do you feel about video making task”? The following are responses from interviewed students.

"Yes, I'm very motivated to participate in video making task. Because it could help train me to improve my speaking skills."

"Yes, I am motivated to learn English using video because i want to be able to speak English."

"Yes, I'm motivated. I'm eager to learn more about English especially speaking so I'm really motivated to participate in video making task given by lecturer."

Despite emergence of dissatisfaction in few students there were more students responded that their inclination to learn improved as a result of video making task.

The second question concerned learning enthusiasm among the students that asked, “How enthusiastic you are about the video making task?”

The responses are as follows

"Not really, sometimes I don't feel enthusiastic about taking videos. Sometimes I feel frustrated because I record videos many times."

"I'm not really motivated to participate in the video task, because as always distracted." "Sometimes, depending on what topics is being taught."

"Sometimes I feel bored when making videos on topics that I don't like."

This transcribed interview demonstrated a relatively high level of dissatisfaction for few learners about video making task. The finding is to some extent could not be over generalized about whether the video making task is detrimental or beneficial.

The third interview question asked regarding level of delivery and material comprehension among that students that asked, *"Did you understand the content of the teaching session and teaching material delivered by the lecturer?"* the responses are as follows

"It's great, even though sometimes I'm distracted by other things I still can manage to understand the materials, because it's clear and the lecturer know when to ask to audience attention, then I'm going to focus to the course topics again. "Lecturer is very well managing the course using video making task."

This transcription imply prevalence of satisfaction about video making task in few of the interviewed students. The finding imply that lecturers need to take account such variables when presenting the task such as video making task. It is even more generalizable that almost all learners were positive about the task from the interview session.

The next important segment of interview indicated that the learners have various responses .The fourth question demanded respondents to state any difficulties they faced when using video making task. Majority of the respondents answered that they face difficulties in their ability to memorize the material that they will convey in video. They also argued that they being shy and feeling awkward have led them to be reluctant to speak in their video. Further, one of the respondents stated that the difficulties in pronounce the right sentence has led the respondent fear to convey the material in video.

"There are difficulties, especially when memorize the materials."

"For me yes, sometimes I feel awkward to speak in front of the camera."

"Yes, it is hard to deliver the materials because I can't pronounce the right sentence."

"Yes, it feels like so shy to speak because there is vocabulary that difficult to pronounce."

Similarly, respondents felt the same when recording their video. One of respondent stated that because they can't pronounce the right sentences so they have to retaking their video until they get the good result.

"Sometimes I have to retake my video because there some vocabulary that difficult to pronounce."

Memory capacity appears to be an issue in the interview that led emergence of difficulty in video making task is memory phone capacity.

"Yes, because sometimes i distracted by my memory phone that already full."

"Yes, there are difficulties, especially with memory phone capacity."

"I'm pretty much having a hard time if the video record goes on suddenly my memory phone is full."

"Sometimes I want to retake my video but the memory already full."

While some experienced difficulties, another did not. One among those who didn't experience such difficulties argued that their constant and daily use video has led them to be accustomed whit it. In addition, the use of video in learning has led students for another alternative for speaking in English.

"I think no difficulties in video making task because I accustomed to using video and recording myself. "Not really, because I can record myself and speaking in English without any difficult."

The fifth question required the respondents to state their experience of self-learning during using video making task in courses. Generally speaking, the respondents showed a mixed response to the question. Some of the argued that it is difficult for them in self-learning or self-correction because they still require a supervision from their lecturer.

"Yes, sometimes I faced difficulties to learn independently and to correct myself in speaking English during delivered the material in video."

"For me during video making we need other people to help and correct us if we were wrong. "Yes, because I am not capable of self-learning, therefore I need to directly discussing the materials with some friends."

"I find it difficult to correct myself in video, but the difficulties are natural for every student, not difficulties that have a big impact."

The emergence of difficulties as evident from the interview imply that video making task gain different perception from a number of students. This imply that the task can be overgeneralized as positive teaching tool to all contexts of students and learning environment.

5.2. Discussions

The discussion under this part addresses two major points that involves statistical data in the forms of tables and qualitative data that involves interview to ensure that triangulation between qualitative and quantitative data was made. The discussion begins with the statistical data that presents *motivation and confidence, learning autonomy, learning focus, learning expectations, and learning experience*. Meanwhile, the interview part will address three related questions

that elicit personal judgment that concern, personal feeling, personal enthusiasm, and individual comprehension regarding classroom performance.

The first important issue is with reference to motivation and confidence. The present study appears to be beneficial in terms of making learners become motivated as shown in table 1. It confirms that the majority of the learners investigated have the tendency of being confident and with high motivation about the task. This imply that video making task could elicit and strengthen the tendency to learn better. As motivation increases will lead to the increase of confidence hence strengthening positive learning environment. Their perception regarding this task is evidently beneficial in terms of making themselves become self-motivated and as such provides a substantial positive learning mood which is essential in enhancing self-confidence.

The second important issue is regarding learning autonomy. Data shows that greater majority of the students investigated perceived if they could become autonomous learners resulting from this video making activity. Only relatively small proportion of these learners confessed themselves if they were not in the position of being autonomous. Despite emergence of this discrepancy, learners were found to be very positive with the obtained percentage of almost hundred percent. This also indicates that the task provides a convenient learning atmosphere which is essential in creating self-image for becoming independent learner. As such, the student take account as contributing factor for directing the class to become learner centered education.

The third important category is with regards to learning focus. According to the obtained data more than 80 percent (80%) of the student surveyed reported perceptions that they have positive focus prior to the implementation of video making task. Despite minority of this issue, learning focus play a vital part in foreign language learning because it relates to attention and concentration. Statistical evidence as shown in the second table where greater majority of students were in favor in this task and hence lead them to have better focus in learning. Creating better learning focus will itself imply generating self-attention to the learning process and as such creating more positive learning outcomes.

The fourth important category is related to learning expectation. It appears that the expectation to learn improved in the majority of the surveyed learners prior to this video making task. Expectation is an issue that teachers or lecturers need to encourage in the classroom because it is a factor that generate learners to learn best. The factor relates to motivation that could be elicit when positive expectation occur in the learners. From the analysis it is becoming prevalent that video making task strengthen the learners expectation so as to provide better leaning environment, especially EFL learning environment. Positive expectation will encourage more convenient process of knowledge transfer which will eventually generate learning motivation.

The final important aspect about the video making task is about learning experiences. Learning experiences are crucial aspect of EFL learning environment because this is the way learners enriched their personality with language acquisition. The analysis demonstrated that video making task tended to enrich learners' learning experiences that lead them to become active learners. From data analysis the study confirms the majority of learners reported perception

about improved and increased learning experiences. This imply that video making task is a rich and manageable classroom tool to enhance positive and cheerful environment. Despite evidence of positive expectation from the learners teachers will need to vary the techniques in implementing the task in order to provide refreshment to prevent learners from being exhausted. Video making task if not treated in such a way could lead to weakening of motivation that can hinder the learners become active learners.

Regarding the result on interview, it is apparent that student's perceptions were in line with what they stated in the interview. Result of interview indicated very high positive in individual or personal feeling as expressed in the form of transcription above. In most cases, the result of interview demonstrated a very high positive in the personal understanding and views about video making task. Emergence of discrepancy in few of the samples interviewed who confessed that they were not really in positive mood indicated that the finding may not be applicable to all learners and as such the findings cannot be generalized. Due to the fact that there is some sort of consistency reported in both questionnaires and interview, the study confirms that video making task may be regarded as vital tool to encourage learner centeredness thus providing a convenient process of making the teaching more productive.

The prevalence of negative feeling and less positive assessment about video making task resulting from the interview may be due to differences in perceiving the fact or differences in personalities, such as learning motivation, learning preferences, and learning expectations. Overall data demonstrated that both through interview and questionnaire checklist had led video making task as beneficial tool in pedagogical practices. Data from the interview may also be regarded as a reliable instrument to validate the data from the questionnaire will imply that the finding has a consistency a valid cross-check of the positive outcomes regarding the use of video making task.

6. CONCLUSION

This research has confirmed varied dimensions about EFL learners in Indonesian context. It appears that video making task concerned various aspects in relation to pedagogy, such as motivation and confidence, learning autonomy, learning focus, learning expectation and learning experiences. Despite limitation of this research in terms of sample homogeneity, questionnaires results demonstrated very high level of finding reliability. This implies that video making task which to some extend is only seen as simple task in English language teaching appears to be beneficial in enriching classroom dynamics. The reliability of research findings is strengthened by the prevalent responses from interview confirming that video making task resulted in personal positive perceptions, such as positive feeling, personal enthusiasm, and improved self-comprehension about teacher's classroom performance. The finding of this research also confirm positive future pedagogical practices where teachers need not only to transfer knowledge but also nurture personalities in order to enable learners engage in positive learning classroom environment. Teachers will constantly need to embark on the importance of empowering video for effective classroom performance.

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